

**THE IMPACT OF JUDICIAL REASSIGNMENT AND THE LEGAL PRINCIPLES FOR ENABLING
JUDICIAL CONSISTENCY IN HIGH PROFILE CASES.**

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the impact of judicial reassignment on the consistency and integrity of legal outcomes, particularly in high-profile cases that attract public and political attention. Judicial reassignment can either be whether due to administrative necessity, perceived bias, or strategic maneuvering which can significantly influence the continuity and coherence of judicial reasoning. The paper critically examines the legal principles and institutional safeguards designed to uphold judicial consistency amidst such transitions, including doctrines of stare decisis, judicial ethics, and procedural fairness.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the Nigerian judicial system and among other judicial system of the world, it is not an uncommon legal practice to have a presiding judge overseeing an ongoing case being transferred or vacated from continuing. This practice usually arises as a result of certain circumstances; such as when the Judge is due for retirement, promotion and maybe had to compulsorily step down due to the necessity of avoiding a conflict of interest.²²² In such cases, another Judge will have to enter into overseeing the case pending the time when the final decision will be determined. The implication of this could inevitably be seen in the delay of justice and bias in the general perception of the public, except where the need for such reassignment is reasonably justified and unquestionable. We must delve into the understanding of the legal principles for enabling judicial consistency, especially when it has to do with high-profile cases.

2. UNDERSTANDING JUDICIAL CONSISTENCY

It should be established that Judicial consistency is a symbol of justice provided for by certain Legal instrument as well as relevant *stare decisis* of higher courts. For instance, *Section 153(1) (i) of the Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria*²²³ clearly stipulates the establishment of the Nigerian Judicial Council. The responsibilities of the Nigerian Judicial Council are further enunciated in *paragraph 21 of the third schedule of the Constitution*,²²⁴ which includes the appointment, promotion, and disciplining of Judicial officers. This specifically connotes the need for transparency and proper regulations in the judicial assignment and reassignment of of judicial officers in any given case. In the same vein, *Article 2.2 of the National Judicial Council Code of Conduct for Judicial Officers* stipulated that where it is discovered that the Integrity of a Judge overseeing a given case will come under a questionable scrutiny of the public, the judge can vacate the case through a reassignment. The necessity for this will be to portray the uncompromising state of the court as a temple of Justice.²²⁵

3. IMPACT OF JUDICIAL REASSIGNMENT

The controversies surrounding reassignment has been notable in the areas of delayed judicial proceedings where the new Judge has to first get himself accustomed to the case at hand before continuing the case. By so doing, the proceedings might be unnecessarily prolonged. Also, there is the probability of the new judge requesting for a *trial de novo*. This is because it cannot be expected that

222 Ojo, MA, 'Judicial Transfers and the Right to Fair Hearing in Nigeria' (2020) 12(2) Nigerian Journal of Constitutional Law 142.

223 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), s 153(1).

224 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), sch 3 pt I para 21.

225 National Judicial Council, Code of Conduct for Judicial Officers of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2016) art 2.2

<<https://njc.gov.ng/files/CODE%20OF%20CONDUCT%20FOR%20JUDICIAL%20OFFICERS.pdf>> accessed 1 May 2025.

both judges would have a similar legal reasoning approach to solving such given legal problems, hence, there is also a high possibility of eroding the former judge's approach if it is not consistent with that of the new Judge. Subsequently, the confidence of the general public in the judicial system might come to a very low ebb, where the concept of justice is seen as denied and biased because it has been delayed. As a matter of facts, the litigants are as well affected largely due to the extent of cost incurred during the proceedings.²²⁶ There is therefore needs to incorporate legitimate practices for the benefit of the Judicial system as a whole.

4. LEGAL PRINCIPLES FOR ENABLING JUDICIAL CONSISTENCY

According to the legal principles established in the case of *MaundisBikaNakai v. FCMB Limited*,²²⁷ where the court was of the position that where a new judge is to preside over an ongoing case, there is a need for a fresh hearing of the trial in order to fulfill the provision for fair hearing. In the light of this, it should be noted that such new Judge should not derogate from the already established principles of law especially where there will be no justified need for doing so. Hence, in the case of *Ojukwu v. Military Governor of Lagos State*,²²⁸ the court held that judicial decisions should not be arbitrarily overturned. The purpose of this will be aimed at arriving at a consistent judicial outcome while still sustaining the doctrine of *Audi AlteramPartem*. In addition, as parts of the stipulated functions of the Nigerian Judicial Council, the choice of reassignment in respect to any case should not be politically driven nor motivated. In order words, the judiciary must ensure that it maintains and sustains its independence from any external force when it comes to decision making. There must be a clear line distinction and integrity to inform a non bias approach towards solving legal issues most especially in high profile cases.

The essence of such carefulness in high profile cases can be seen in the possible aggravation of public perception and possible violence if care is not taken. Most people might easily form the opinion of political interference , thereby contributing to their distrust in the system and possible insurrection. Take for instance, the high profile case of NnamdiKanu has been ongoing for about nine years since his arrest in the year 2015 with up to four judges having presided over his case.²²⁹ Justice BintaNyako had to recused herself from the case on September 24, 2024 given the allegation of partiality from the observers. Following this, the Chief Judge of the Federal High Court reassigned the case to Justice

226Olakulehin OO, 'Access to Justice and the Cost of Litigation in Nigeria: Rethinking the Legal Framework' (2021) 9(1) Nigerian Journal of Law and Practice 114 <<https://lawandpractice.ng/publications/access-to-justice-cost-of-litigation-in-nigeria.pdf>> accessed 1 May 2025.

227MaundisBikaNakai v First City Monument Bank Ltd, (NICN/YL/01/2016).

228Ojukwu v Military Governor of Lagos State (1986) 1 NWLR (Pt. 18) 621.

229Arogbonlo I, 'Explainer: Why Justice Nyako Stepped Down from NnamdiKanu's Trial' (2024) Nigerian Tribune <<https://tribuneonlineng.com/explainer-why-justice-nyako-stepped-down-from-nnamdi-kanus-trial/>> accessed 1 May 2025.

James Omotosho who is currently to preside over the case. Prior to this period, Justice Jummai Hanatu Sankey had presided over the panel that dismissed the 15 count terrorism charge against him alongside another Judge. The extent of responses witnessed from concerned citizens, members of the Eastern Nigeria, Human Rights Advocate, International agencies largely infer the need for judicial consistency and integrity.

Judicial consistency is a fundamental requirement for the credibility and integrity of any legal system, particularly in high-profile cases where public scrutiny is intense. One of the foundational legal principles that ensures consistency is the doctrine of stare decisis, this doctrine is based on the principle of judicial precedents, where courts rely on the Court's decision in a previously decided case having similar facts with the one being considered. The essence of relying on the past decision of the court is to allow consistency in reaching the Court's overall judgement. Hence, what was decided in a previous case should not be far from what will be decided in any ongoing similar case. This will help in sustaining the consistency of judicial decision without bias. Even though a judicial reassignment might be considered necessary, such will be done with the view of following the already laid down principles of judicial precedent. Subsequently, the judges will be helped to make a well-informed and uniformed judgement.²³⁰

The rule of law itself is another essential legal principle for ensuring judicial consistency. This means that any assigned or re-assigned Judge in respect to any case (especially high-profile cases) , must yield the principle of rule of law.²³¹ They must consider the supremacy of law over and above all other decisions to be taken. The problem however is most times, the rule of law is often discarded and sacrificed in exchange for "the rule of the rulers". Subsequently, the ruling politicians are mostly at the centre of influencing judicial decisions in the reassignment of judges in order to facilitate a favourable stance or position for their mutual and political benefits.

Genuine judicial independence is equally crucial for achieving consistency. Judges must be free from external pressures and influences so that they can base their decisions solely on legal reasoning. Independence must be institutional and operational, encompassing secure tenure, adequate remuneration, and financial autonomy for the judiciary. Without independence, the risk of inconsistent

230 Nelson U. Sobere, 'Applicability of the Doctrine of Judicial Precedent in Nigeria: The Case of Ibrahim v Judicial Service Commission, Kaduna State & Another in Focus' (2024) 1 Nigerian Journal of Law and Practice <<https://journal.nials.edu.ng/index.php/nclr/article/view/26>> accessed 1 May 2025.

231 Evangelle Austin-Amadi, 'The Relationship Between the Rule of Law and Constitutional Democracy in the Nigerian Context' (2016) Nigerian Journal of Law and Practice <https://www.academia.edu/105942709/Rule_of_Law_in_Nigeria> accessed 1 May 2025.

rulings influenced by non-legal factors increases, especially in sensitive or politically charged matters. Hence, the activities of members of the executive and legislative arms of government should not be a deciding factor for Judges to reaching their overall judgement in any given judicial case.

5. CONCLUSION.

Judicial consistency in high-profile cases relies on the various principles examined to enabling such consistency. The Judiciary must therefore take into considerations the various measures already established in respect to maintaining a consistent judicial decisions void of partiality and injustice. Also, judicial reassignment should be seen as an instrument to proclaiming fair hearing and not to propagate injustice or politically motivated decisions

6. RECOMMENDATION.

1. Courts should provide well-structured and detailed judgments explaining the application of legal principles to case facts.
2. Emphasize comprehensive legal reasoning to promote continuity and accountability.
3. Encourage judges to critically evaluate and assess facts before reaching conclusions.
4. Implement regular judicial training on legal developments, consistency, and comparative analysis.
5. Appoint judges based on proven scholarly and legal expertise.
6. Establish credible and robust judicial training programs.
7. Improve internal communication and coordination within and across courts.
8. Develop institutional frameworks for knowledge-sharing and peer consultations.
9. Standardize and encourage the publication and dissemination of judgments, including from lower courts.
10. Modernize court processes through digital technologies and case management systems.
11. Utilize technology to reduce human error, streamline workloads, and ensure uniform application of legal principles.